

Principal Leadership Contribution and Teacher Competence in Improving Teacher Performance

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received March 04, 2021

Revised March 05, 2021

Accepted July 24, 2021

Available online August 25, 2021

Kata Kunci :

Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah,
Kompetensi Guru, Kinerja Guru

Keywords:

Principal Leadership, Teacher
Competence, Teacher Performance

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ABSTRAK

Keberhasilan sekolah dalam melaksanakan proses pembelajaran yang efektif dan efisien bukanlah suatu usaha yang sederhana, melainkan suatu kegiatan yang dinamis dan penuh tantangan. Parameter keberhasilan yang diterapkan dalam proses belajar mengajar seorang guru tidak hanya terkait dengan jumlah prestasi yang telah dicapai guru tetapi juga dengan optimalisasi kinerjanya. Oleh karena itu, peningkatan kinerja guru perlu mendapat perhatian serius dari berbagai pihak termasuk sekolah sebagai dasar untuk mengambil langkah konkrit terkait peningkatan faktor kinerja guru seperti kepemimpinan kepala sekolah dan kompetensi guru. Optimalisasi kinerja seorang guru sangat penting untuk menunjang proses pembelajaran yang berkualitas. Untuk mendukung peningkatan kinerja guru, diperlukan peran penting dalam gaya kepemimpinan kepala sekolah, dan kompetensi guru secara komprehensif. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis pengaruh kepemimpinan kepala sekolah dan kompetensi guru terhadap kinerja guru. Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kuantitatif kausalitas. Pengumpulan data dilakukan melalui dokumentasi dan angket. Penelitian ini menggunakan sampel sebanyak 98 responden dengan penentuan ukuran sampel menggunakan rumus sampel jenuh. Kuadrat terkecil parsial diterapkan untuk menguji hubungan antara kinerja guru, kepemimpinan kepala sekolah, dan kompetensi guru. Hasil penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa variabel kepemimpinan kepala sekolah memiliki kontribusi yang signifikan terhadap peningkatan kinerja guru. Lebih lanjut, kompetensi yang dimiliki oleh seorang guru juga memiliki kontribusi yang signifikan terhadap peningkatan kinerja guru.

ABSTRACT

The success of schools in implementing an effective and efficient learning process is not a simple effort, but an activity that is dynamic and full of challenges. The success parameters that are applied in the teaching and learning process of a teacher include not only those related to the number of achievements the teacher has achieved but also with the optimization of their performance. Therefore, improving teacher performance needs serious attention from various parties including schools as a basis for taking concrete steps related to improving teacher performance factors such as principal leadership and teacher competence. Optimizing the performance of a teacher is very important to support a quality learning process. To support the improvement of a teacher's performance, a crucial role in the leadership style of the principal, and the competence of teachers in a comprehensive manner is needed. This study aims to analyze the effect of principal leadership and teacher competence on teacher performance. This research uses a quantitative approach to causality. Data were collected through documentation and questionnaires. This study used a sample of 98 respondents with the determination of the sample size using the saturated sample formula. A partial least square is applied to examine the relationship between teacher performance, principal leadership, and teacher competence. The results of this study indicate that the principal's leadership variable has a significant contribution to improving teacher performance. Furthermore, the competencies possessed by a teacher also have a significant contribution to improving teacher performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of schools in implementing an effective and efficient learning process is not a simple effort, but an activity that is dynamic and full of challenges (Nugraheni & Rahmayanti, 2016). The success parameters that are applied in the teaching and learning process of a teacher include not only those related to the number of achievements the teacher has achieved but also with the optimization of their performance (Lie et al., 2019). The achievement of a teacher in carrying out his duties following the responsibilities given to him is representative of the successful performance of a teacher (Novitasari et al., 2012). The optimal representation of teacher performance will help schools to teach students in a better

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direction (Siregar & Thomas, 2014). Optimizing teacher performance is the main target in improving the quality of education in general (Firmawati et al., 2017). Therefore, improving teacher performance needs serious attention from various parties including schools as a basis for taking concrete steps related to improving teacher performance factors such as principal leadership and teacher competence (Indajang et al., 2020).

Every education unit, including schools, really needs optimal teacher performance. Teacher performance is an important target in human resource management because it will directly or indirectly affect work productivity (Setianigsih & Kader, 2018). Teacher teaching performance is the teacher's performance in managing learning as a concrete realization of the competencies they have based on skills, experience, and sincerity (Sobandi, 2010). Furthermore, teacher performance is the teacher's effort to improve student achievement through teaching (Wahyudi et al., 2014). The level of teacher performance is not only closely related to the reward system but also has a relationship with the leadership of the principal applied by the leader where they work and the high motivation of a teacher (Husna, 2017). Optimal teacher performance is reflected in work quality, work accuracy, work initiative, work skills, and communication. Thus, the comprehensive maintenance of teacher performance is needed in implementing quality education (Utari & Rasto, 2019).

To produce the best human resources, a teacher needs a role in carrying out his duties effectively (Darwin, 2018). Many factors affect the level of performance, one of which is the leadership of the principal (Liu & Hallinger, 2018). The principal is someone who determines the center point and rhythm of a school. Because the school is a complex institution, the school as an organization requires coordination with every element in it (Setiyati, 2014). Efforts to integrate organizational or personal interests to achieve certain goals require careful consideration of a leader as a managerial decision-maker (Purwanto et al., 2020). Over the last few decades, many studies have stated and attempted to validate the relationship between principal leadership, teacher performance, and student learning processes in supporting quality improvement in schools (Zheng et al., 2017). In creating a vision and mission and determining school strategies and policies, the essence of the presence of a school principal as a leader is needed (Rokhani, 2020). The principal as a leader must be able to provide guidance and supervision, increase the willingness of education personnel, open two-way communication, and delegate tasks (Ngiode, 2016). The role of the principal is very crucial in empowering teachers to work more productively to achieve quality learning (Astuti & Dacholfany, 2016). Previous research conveyed that there was a significant influence between the leadership applied by the principal and teacher performance (Halim, 2016; Ideswal et al., 2020). Further research stated that the increase in teacher performance does not have a significant relationship with the leadership applied by the principal (Yaman, 2020).

In achieving performance optimization, a teacher must be able to develop all of his abilities related to competence and create a learning atmosphere that is more comfortable and conducive for his students (Haryani & Cahyaningtyas, 2017). Therefore, a teacher is expected to be able to improve the quality of education for the benefit of the school system, have life skills, a good mastery of science and technology, and a professional character based on their competencies (Sayer et al., 2018). Competence is a general term for the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for an adequate function in a particular profession (Sukamto & Pardjono, 2016). The ability of teachers to understand rules and implement proper rules, both concerning other personnel at school and in the teaching and learning process in the classroom greatly helps improve the quality of the learning process in the classroom (Siregar & Thomas, 2014). In addition to the leading factor of the principal, the competence of a teacher is also related to improving the performance of a teacher (Sherly et al., 2020). Competence is one of the factors that affect employee performance because if the work assigned to an employee is under the ability of the employee concerned, then he will work seriously and be well-disciplined to do it (Heriswanto, 2018). The professionalism of a teacher in teaching will be seen from the mastery of sub-competency structures and scientific methods in certain fields so that the implications of this mastery are believed to be able to improve performance (Hafid, 2017). Based on the results of previous research, there is a significant impact on teacher competence on teacher performance (Haryani & Cahyaningtyas, 2017). Another research states that teacher performance is not significantly influenced by the competence of a teacher (Rahardjo, 2014).

The results of previous studies concluded different results, thus opening the gap for researchers to re-examine. Researchers have the opportunity to conduct further research related to principal leadership and teacher competence which is thought to affect teacher performance levels based on the theories supported above (the gap phenomenon and research gap). The main objective of this research is to find out how big the role of principal leadership and teacher competence is in influencing the level of teacher performance of the Sultan Agung Pematangsiantar Foundation, North Sumatra.

2. METHODS

The method with the quantitative causality approach used in this study is oriented towards a theoretical model which is assessed by PLS-SEM analysis in a two-stage process. First, the research data were analyzed for validity and reliability using Cronbach's alpha testing, composite reliability, outer loading, and average variance extracted. Then, perform Confirmatory Factor Analysis to check the fit of the model and model reliability and discuss hypotheses through variance-based Structural Equation Model (SEM) (Hair, 2014). To determine the sample size, the saturated sample method is used. The saturated sampling technique was used based on the entire study population being sampled as a whole. The sample that will be used in this research is all the teachers of the Sultan Agung College of Education, totaling 98 people. The instrument used for this study used a questionnaire using a Likert scale, namely (1) which stated "very dissatisfied to" (5) "very satisfied". The measurement of the dependent and independent variables uses previous references that are relevant to the research topic and research variables. Measurement of the dependent variable, namely teacher performance is measured using Undang-Undang Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 Tentang Guru Dan Dosen about Teachers and Lecturers which consists of 3 indicators. Furthermore, for the first independent variable, the principal's leadership is measured using Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Nasional Nomor 13 Tahun 2007 Tentang Standar Kepala Sekolah / Madrasah regarding Principal Standards for Schools / Madrasahs which consists of 5 indicators. Then for the second independent variable, namely teacher competence is measured using Undang-Undang Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 Tentang Guru Dan Dosen Pasal 8 which consists of 4 indicators.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

The distribution of questionnaires was carried out conventionally by meeting directly with Sultan Agung Foundation teachers and online via WhatsApp and Telegram social media. The number of respondents who filled out the questionnaire was 98 teachers. The general characteristics of respondents in this study will clearly be described in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Detail	total	Percentage
Gender	Men	23	23.47%
	Woman	75	76.53%
Age	<20 years	1	1.02%
	21-30 years	13	13.27%
	31-40 years	34	34.69%
	41-50 years	23	23.47%
	> 50 years	27	27.55%
Level of education	High school	2	2.04%
	Bachelor degree	81	82.65%
	Strata 2	15	15.31%
Work unit	Kindergarten	15	15.31%
	SD	33	33.67%
	Junior High	22	23.47%
	High school	28	27.55%
Years of service	<5 years	15	15.31%
	6-10 Years	21	21.43%
	11-20 Years	30	30.61%
	21-30 Years	17	17.35%
	> 20 Years	15	15.31%

Outlier Model Measurement

The results of the data obtained from the research questionnaire were processed using the SmartPLS version 3.2.9 application with management guidelines from (Juliandi, 2018). In measuring the outer model, the tests carried out are validity tests and reliability tests. Convergent validity testing is determined by the loading factor and AVE with the condition that the loading factor is above 0.7 and the AVE value is 0.5 (Hair, 2014). Model reliability testing seen from the value of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) which has a value greater than 0.7 (Hair, 2014). The following will display an explanation of the measurement of the outlier model which is presented using Table 2.

Table 2. Outlier Model Measurement Results

Construct / item	Outlier Loadings	Cronbach 'alpha	CR	AVE
Principal Leadership		0.928	0.946	0.777
KEP1	0.926			
KEP2	0.843			
KEP3	0.868			
KEP4	0.858			
KEP5	0.910			
Teacher Competence		0.955	0.968	0.882
KT1	0.963			
KT2	0.929			
KT3	0.904			
KT4	0.958			
Teacher Performance		0.928	0.954	0.874
KG1	0.953			
KG2	0.957			
KG3	0.893			

In the validity test presented in Table 2, it is known that the value of each loading factor on the variable indicator of school principal leadership, organizational culture, teacher competence, and teacher performance is above 0.7 and above 0.5 for the average variance value. extracted (AVE). Furthermore, the value for each of the above reliability is obtained by the composite reliability value for each research variable is above 0.7 which can be explained as follows: principal leadership obtained 0.946, teacher competence obtained 0.968, and teacher performance obtained 0.954. Furthermore, for the Cronbach's alpha value, the value for each variable was above 0.7, which indicates that all research variables had a good reliability value.

Inner Model Measurement

Inner model measurement is done by bootstrapping research data using SmartPLS 3.2.9. There are two results obtained from bootstrapping, the first is the significance of the two related variables, and also the R-square of the study. The value of the R-square is a value that shows the ability of exogenous variables to build endogenous variables. There are three categories of R-square value, if the R-square value is 0.19, the relationship between exogenous variables forming endogenous variables is weak, if it is 0.33 it means the relationship is moderate and if the value is 0.67 it indicates that the relationship is strong (Chin et al., 2008). If the R-square value is more than 0.67, the relationship between endogenous and exogenous is very strong (Sarwono, 2016). Judging from the R-square value for endogenous variables, the value is 0.117, which value is below 0.19, this shows that overall the ability of exogenous variables to explain endogenous variables is weak. Furthermore, to prove the hypothesis testing, a significance test is used to determine the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables. The criterion for significance is seen from the p-value. With a significance level of 5%, if the p-value between the exogenous and endogenous variables is less than 0.05, it means that the exogenous variable has a significant effect on the endogenous variable, on the other hand, if the value is greater than 0.05, it means that the exogenous variable has no significant effect in building endogenous variables.

Table 3. Path Coefficients Test Results

Path	Coefficient	t-count	P-Value	Conclusion
Principals Leadership >> Teachers' Performance	0.201	2.255	0.025	Accepted
Teachers' Competences >> Teachers' Performance	0.259	2.674	0.008	Accepted

Based on the results of the processed data presented in Table 3, the significance test of the direct relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables can be said that overall exogenous variables have a significant effect on endogenous variables. The principal of the teacher performance variable has a significant effect on the results of the teacher competency variable on the teacher performance variable, the results also have a significant effect

Discussion

The Effect of Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

The results showed that the principal's leadership had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. The findings of this study are consistent with the results of the study (Setiyati, 2014) and (Rokhani, 2020), whose research results state that there is no significant influence between principal leadership on teacher performance. Representatives of the leadership presence of the principal will be seen when devoting his ability to carry out his duties to achieve goals (Astuti & Dacholfany, 2016). In an organization, a leader is needed to direct its members in running the organization in order to achieve the expected goals. The leader will not be able to control the members if he does not have a good leadership style. So how important the leadership style is in improving performance. With the leadership style that is applied, it will be able to control and maintain the performance of the members. Thus the performance will be optimal and as expected by the organization itself. The abilities that a leader must have, in this case, the principal, are to have a personality that is an example to his subordinates, the ability to motivate, make decisions, communicate and delegate authority (Juniarti et al., 2020). On the other hand, the results of this study are not in line with the research presented by (Gandung, 2019), which states that there is no significant influence between principal leadership on teacher performance. The leadership of a school principal that is not following school rules and is not in line with the vision and mission of the school is not able to encourage an increase in teacher performance (Yaman, 2020).

The Effect of Teacher Competence on Teacher Performance

The results showed that teacher competence had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. The findings of this study are in line with the results of the study (Pakpahan et al., 2019) and (Tafqihan & Suryanto, 2014), which states that the significant increase in teacher performance is due to the competence of a teacher. This is because the competence of a teacher is a reflection of the skills and attitudes needed to produce good quality teaching for students (Sukamto & Pardjono, 2016). The importance of competency-based teacher performance development is one of the efforts made to improve performance. Competency-based teacher performance development is a form of recognition and attention from superiors to teachers who are able to show skill, work ability, and obedience and work discipline that is realized by real work. The higher the competence of employees and being able to match the demands of the job, the teacher's performance will increase because teachers who are competent usually have the ability and also a fast willingness to solve work problems at hand, do work with dedication, calm and full of confidence. , views work as an obligation that must be done sincerely and openly to improve one's quality through the learning process. However, several studies conducted the same study that obtained different results from the results of this study. Previous study states that there is no significant influence between teacher competence on teacher performance (Narsih, 2017). Even though a teacher has adequate competence, the incentives provided are not following the measure of his competence, so the teacher does not have high morale so that it can hinder his performance (Rahardjo, 2014).

4. CONCLUSION

From the results of hypothesis testing and evaluation that has been described by the author, it can be concluded that the principal's leadership affects the increase in teacher performance. The performance of teachers in an organization or school can be influenced by their leadership style. Many factors can improve performance, one of which is that effective and efficient leadership can certainly shape and improve performance. With the leadership style effectively and efficiently implemented by the organization, it will shape and improve teacher performance. Furthermore, the influence of teacher competence on teacher performance also obtained significant results. This is because if a person has a positive personality such as being willing to accept other people's opinions and is open to all the knowledge given, then of course that person is able to develop his / her competences, so that with good competency abilities, it can affect the performance it produces in carry out the duties and responsibilities assigned to him. Then for the R-square value for endogenous variables shows that overall the ability of exogenous variables to explain endogenous variables is weak. For further research, it is necessary to add a larger number of respondents so that the research can be generalized and include new variables that are thought to affect teacher performance, such as compensation, commitment, work environment, work ethic, reward, and work discipline so that they can be used as input for the Foundation. Sultan Agung College and Pematangsiantar City Education Authority in determining policies related to improving teacher performance.

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